

Prevalence of excess binaural broadband loudness sensitivity in the hearing-impaired population and implications for hearing aid gain targets

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ABSTRACT

Previous studies reported large individual differences of loudness sensitivity to binaural broadband sounds in hearing-impaired listeners after narrowband loudness was normalized. These differences in loudness sensitivity might be linked to substantial fine-tuning necessary for many hearing aid users to achieve acceptable loudness in daily use. The present study aims at characterizing the binaural broadband loudness sensitivity in the hearing-impaired population, the prevalence of higher-than-normal values, and the potential implications for hearing aid target gains.

In 180 hearing-impaired participants we measured standard audiological diagnostic parameters, binaural broadband loudness sensitivity and computed gain targets according to NAL-NL2, DSLm[i/o] and trueLOUDNESS, a previously described prescriptive procedure that includes individual loudness measurements. 160 participants were recruited and measured at hearing aid professionals' facilities, while 20 participants were recruited from a research database and measured in a laboratory using the same hardware.

The observed aided binaural broadband loudness sensitivity in hearing impaired participants was, on average, elevated and showed a higher variance compared to a normal-hearing reference group. Participants recruited in hearing aid professionals' facilities showed a higher prevalence of higher-than-normal binaural broadband loudness sensitivity (40% of participants) than those from the study database (30% of participants). The average excess loudness sensitivity appears to be included in established prescriptive procedures, while relevant differences to trueLOUDNESS gain targets were observed in more than half of the participants. Elevated loudness sensitivity to binaural broadband sounds appears to be a prevalent and individual trait in the hearing-impaired population and might be useful for individualized hearing aid fitting.

1. Introduction

Gain prescription procedures for hearing aids aim at compensating for perceptual effects of hearing impairment, including loss of audibility, impaired speech intelligibility and altered loudness perception by application of frequency and level-dependent gain (Dillon, 2012; Kollmeier and Kiessling, 2018). To obtain gain targets, most prescriptive procedures take the hearing threshold from the audiogram as the main input, potentially supplemented by other metrics such as the Uncomfortable Loudness Level (UCL), the air-bone-gap or personal data like age or gender. Although discussed in academic research for considerable amount of time, no current practically used prescriptive procedure considers suprathreshold parameters except UCLs. The current best-practice prescriptive procedures thus neglect the commonly accepted understanding that a lot of individual variation of audiological outcomes across hearing-impaired listeners exists that is not captured by the audiogram (Jepsen and Dau, 2011; Kiessling et al., 1996; Kortlang et al., 2016; Saak et al., 2022; Sanchez Lopez et al., 2018). In many cases, substantial fine-tuning of gains is necessary to reach a satisfactory outcome for the hearing aid user, for which no or only little formal guidance exists (Anderson et al., 2018; Dillon, 2012; Keidser et al., 2012).

Common non-proprietary prescription procedures thereby follow different approaches to compensating the consequences of hearing loss (Dillon, 2012). NAL-NL2 aims at maximizing speech intelligibility while limiting the overall loudness to normal or less-than-normal (Byrne et al., 2001; Keidser et al., 2011). DSLm[i/o] aims at loudness normalization based on the hearing threshold (Scollie et al., 2005). CAMEQ and CAM2 attempt to equalize loudness of speech across frequency while limiting the overall loudness to a normal-hearing level (Moore et al., 2010). All prescription procedures thereby rely on computational models of the (impaired) auditory system for obtaining prescribed insertion gains. Such models are usually

optimized to represent the average listener with a given audiogram, and in principle cannot account for individual supra-threshold factors.

In the context of loudness-based hearing aid fitting, Oetting et al. (2016) reported on individually different loudness perception of binaurally presented, broadband sounds, which could not be predicted based on monaural, narrowband loudness functions or hearing thresholds. This effect, in the following referred to excess loudness sensitivity, was reproduced in several studies and using various measurement methods (Ewert and Oetting, 2018; Oetting et al., 2019a; Van Beurden et al., 2021, 2018; Zimmer et al., 2024). By considering the individual excess loudness summation in a dynamic compression framework considering the ‘binaurality’ and bandwidth of the input signals, Oetting et al. (2018) were able to restore normal loudness perception also for binaural broadband sounds in a number of listeners with variable excess loudness summation. Assuming that most relevant everyday sounds are broadband and binaurally received, the individual excess loudness summation together with narrowband loudness functions can be used to obtain individual prescriptive hearing aid gain targets. The procedure can be considerably speeded up by estimation of the narrowband loudness functions from the audiogram, without significant loss of accuracy (Suck et al., 2020). The resulting prescription procedure is termed trueLOUDNESS, taking as input the air conduction hearing thresholds of both ears and the categorical loudness function for a binaurally presented female speech-shaped noise that includes simulated narrowband loudness normalization based on the hearing thresholds. The relation of the individual loudness function thus gives insights to the level-dependent aided loudness sensitivity in relation to normal-hearing listeners. This information is then used to adapt the gain targets on top of the underlying hearing threshold-based narrowband loudness normalization. Various evaluation studies showed more natural loudness perception and equivalent speech intelligibility outcomes compared to NAL-NL2 (Kramer et al., 2020; Oetting et al., 2019b). However, previous studies

assessed only a limited number of participants and did not systematically assess the differences of resulting gain targets to established prescription procedures.

In the present investigation, we aim at characterizing the prevalence of excess loudness sensitivity to binaural broadband sounds in the hearing-impaired population, and the relevance for resulting hearing aid target gain predictions. To this end, a multi-centre study was conducted to recruit participants as close as possible from the regular pool of hearing-impaired persons seeking hearing aid treatment. 160 participants were recruited and measured at five hearing aid professionals' facilities (HAPFs) across Germany. Additionally, 20 participants were recruited from a database of regularly requested hearing aid test participants maintained by the German Institute of Hearing Aids (Deutsches Hörgeräte Institut, DHI) Lübeck, and measured in its laboratories using the same hardware as in the HAPFs. Further, a normal-hearing reference group (N=20) underwent the identical measurements at DHI. Measurements included an extended set of standard audiologic diagnostic parameters, the IHS questionnaire on hyperacusis (Greenberg and Carlos, 2018), and categorical loudness scaling that included simulated narrowband loudness compensation (Suck et al., 2020). Further, gain targets were computed for all participants using trueLOUDNESS, NAL-NL2 and DSLm[i/o]. This rich database allows an assessment of the occurrence of excess loudness sensitivity in the target population, potential audiological predictors of this parameter, and the deviations of the resulting gain targets from established rules in the same participants.

2. Measurements

2.1. Procedure

The study protocol was kept as close as possible to the hearing assessment part of a regular hearing aid fitting appointment in a HAPF in Germany. It included query of personal data (age, gender) and existing hearing aid provision (type of hearing aids and coupling, years of hearing

aid experience). Further, extensive audiometric measurements were made. This included air conduction thresholds using sine tones at 11 audiometric frequencies between 125 Hz and 8 kHz, bone conduction thresholds and uncomfortable loudness levels (UCLs) at 500 Hz, 1 kHz, 2 kHz and 4 kHz, all at left and right ears. Further UCLs were measured for speech (Freiburg polysyllabic numbers material) on the left and right ear monaurally as well as with diotic presentations, all over headphones. Additionally, the participants completed the IHS questionnaire on signs of hyperacusis (Greenberg and Carlos, 2018)

In a second step, categorical loudness functions were measured for three stimuli as outlined by (Suck et al., 2020), which is a shortened procedure of the one employed by Oetting et al. (2016). The stimuli presented by the audiometer included simulated hearing aid amplification to compensate for narrowband loudness recruitment as estimated from the hearing thresholds, and thus can be interpreted as aided measurements with a gain prescription aiming for loudness normalization based on narrowband loudness functions. Loudness functions were measured adaptively (Brand and Hohmann, 2002) and sequentially for three stimuli: 1) a unified excitation noise (UEN, creating equal power in each auditory filter band according to (Zwicker, 1961)) with 5 critical bands bandwidth (800-1300Hz), 2) a 17 critical bands wide UEN (500-4000 Hz) and 3) the International Female speech-shaped Noise (IFnoise) obtained from the International Speech Test Signal (Holube et al., 2010). For further evaluations, only the result of the IFnoise loudness function is considered.

All measurements were conducted using the ACAM5 audiometer (Acousticon, Reinheim, Germany) with firmware version 5.22.13Rev5123 and the trueLOUDNESS model installed, which implements the method explained in the previous paragraph using the extra-aural A2000 headphone (Acousticon, Reinheim, Germany). The audiometric thresholds were measured using headphones that varied between measurement sites. All measurements were conducted by trained HAPFs in appropriately treated acoustic test rooms.

2.2. Multi-centre design and participant recruitment

The study aimed at recruiting a broad range of hearing-impaired participants representing the typical cohort of individuals seeking hearing aid treatment. Inclusion criteria for the participants were at least 18 years of age, an audiometric hearing loss of at least 30 dB between 500 Hz and 4 kHz in the better ear, and a difference of PTA hearing thresholds between ears of no more than 15 dB to exclude strongly asymmetric hearing losses. Further, participants could either be “New” (no more than 3 months after initial fit) or “Experienced” hearing aid users (at least two years of continuous use), with the intention to recruit approximately equal numbers in both categories. Exclusion criteria were the use of any hearing implants.

To be able to recruit participants as close as possible to audiological practice, the main part of the measurements was conducted at five HAPFs across Germany. The study protocol was issued by the DHI, who supervised the data collection and performed all evaluation. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Lübeck (vote 2024-108). Participants were recruited by employees of the HAPFs among their regular clients on a voluntary basis. They gave written informed consent to participate in the study before any data collection beyond their regular appointment was made. All collaborators were instructed to not consider any prior audiological history of the clients for the invitation, except for meeting inclusion criteria. The collaborating HAPFs were reimbursed for the data collection based on the number of contributed datasets. It was set at their liberty whether their participants were reimbursed. Data was transmitted to DHI through a password-protected cloud storage system in a pseudonymized way under a HAPF-specific client ID. In this way, only the HAPFs was able to link the study data to a person. Personal base data and the IHS responses were inserted in an Excel document, while the results of audiometry and loudness scaling could be exported automatically from the audiometer software. A total of 160 hearing-impaired individuals participated through the HAPFs, including 88 New users.

In addition to the measurements in HAPFs, the identical measurements were performed in laboratories of the DHI. On the one hand, this included a cohort of 20 experienced hearing aid users recruited from a database that regularly participate in hearing studies. This group is referred to “Experimenters” in the following. On the other hand, 20 young normal hearing participants (18-25 of age, hearing thresholds max. 15 dB HL at no more than 2 frequencies between 250 Hz and 8 kHz per ears) underwent the measurements for reference purposes. The results from the normal-hearing participants reproduced previous data obtained with different hardware very well (Oetting et al., 2016). The normal-hearing data from the current evaluation is used as a normal-hearing reference.

2.3. Gain target computation

Based on the audiometric measurements, third-octave target insertion gains for a speech signal according to common prescriptive procedures were calculated for all participants. Gains were computed for the NAL-NL2 (Keidser et al., 2012, 2011), DSL multistage input-output (DSLm[i/o]) (Scollie et al., 2005) and trueLOUDNESS (Oetting et al., 2017; Suck et al., 2020) prescription procedures. NAL-NL2 is probably the most commonly used non-proprietary prescription rule in both research and clinical applications, and was developed to maximize speech intelligibility while keeping loudness normal or less-than-normal. NAL-NL2 gains were computed using its dll engine (Version 2.15) and the openMHA NAL-NL2 wrapper (2023) to invoke the 32-Bit dll engine out of Matlab R2024b. All air and bone conduction thresholds and the participant’s age and gender were used as input. Target insertion gains were computed for a bilateral fitting, a non-tonal language, slow compression speed, and an experienced adult user. The rationale of DSLm[i/o] gain prescription is to achieve audibility while avoiding loudness discomfort. DSLm[i/o] gain targets were computed through an automated access to an online tool (<https://core.dslio.com/>), using the audiograms and UCLs as input, with no wideband correction and the quiet program. DSLm[i/o] by default assumes different spectral shapes of

the input signal at different input levels to account for effects of vocal effort. To be able to compare insertion gain targets to the other prescription procedures, we here used IFnoise spectra at appropriate levels as input also for DSLm[i/o]. Note that bone-conduction thresholds are not used by the DSLm[i/o] algorithm if UCL measurements are available. The trueLOUDNESS prescription procedure aims at normalizing binaural broadband loudness as measured by categorical loudness functions, combining narrowband loudness curves estimated from the hearing threshold and measurements of the binaural broadband loudness function (Oetting et al., 2017; Suck et al., 2020). Gain targets according to the trueLOUDNESS rule were computed on the ACAM5 audiometer and exported together with the loudness functions (see above).

Target gains were computed for input levels at 50, 65, and 80 dB broadband speech level for all frequencies available in the appropriate tools. Comparisons were made for insertion gains at 500, 1000, 2000 and 4000 Hz. It was a-priori determined that a significant difference between gain targets is reached if the unsigned error between prescription procedures, averaged across all considered levels, frequencies and both ears, exceeds 5 dB. Further, the compression ratio between a *high* and *low* broadband input level L_{in} at each frequency was computed based on the gains G for these input levels

$$CR_{high-low} = \frac{\Delta L_{in}}{\Delta L_{in} + G(L_{in}^{(high)}) - G(L_{in}^{(low)})}. \quad (1)$$

3. RESULTS & ANALYSIS

3.1. Characteristics of participant population

Figure 1 shows the pooled air conduction hearing thresholds and UCLs of all participants. The participants cover a wide range from moderate to profound hearing losses, with an average

close to the N3 type hearing loss (Bisgaard et al., 2010). The UCLs vary between 80 and 120 dB HL, with an average close to 100 dB HL across all regarded frequencies.

Figure 1: Air-conduction thresholds (black) and UCLs (red) for all participants, thick lines showing averages. Solid lines show data for left ears, dashed lines for right ears.

Figure 2 shows the age and average hearing thresholds (Pure Tone Average across 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz, PTA) distribution of the participants between the predefined groups. Differences between groups were assessed using an unpaired t -tests including Bonferroni corrections. Regarding PTA, a significant difference was observed between New users and the other two groups (both $p < 0.001$), showing that the New users had lower PTA thresholds, and no significant difference was observed between Experienced users and the Experimenters group. Regarding age, no statistically significant difference was observed between the groups. However, there is a trend that the New users were the youngest (70.9 ± 11.4 years, mean + standard deviation), followed by the Experienced users from the field (72.7 ± 11.3 years), and the Experimenters group, which had the highest age (75.9 ± 12.3 years).

Figure 2: Distribution of age and PTA thresholds divided by participant groups. Horizontal lines indicate the median, boxes the interquartile range, and whiskers the full data range excluding outliers (crosses).

3.2. Excess loudness sensitivity

Figure 3: Loudness functions for IFnoise with narrowband loudness normalization, showing hearing-impaired participants (gray lines, thick black line showing average) and normal-hearing reference function (thick green line).

Figure 3 shows all obtained loudness functions obtained in the hearing-impaired participants for the IFnoise signal, the average (level averaged for each CU), and the normal-hearing reference function. A wide distribution of loudness functions is observed, where the variation

largely increases with input level. The 95% range of ratings of 40 CU (between “loud” and “very loud”) after simulated amplification is seen for input levels between 45.8 and 94.3 dB SPL, with an average of 69.3 dB SPL. In comparison, the appropriate range of input levels for normal-hearing listeners lies between 63.6 and 102.8 dB SPL, with an average of 82.3 dB SPL.

For further evaluations, the difference in input level at 40 CU (ΔL_{40}) between a participant (L_{40}) and the normal-hearing average (L_{40}^{ref}) is considered

$$\Delta L_{40} = L_{40}^{ref} - L_{40}. \quad (2)$$

A positive value of ΔL_{40} thus indicates that a rating of 40 CU was reached at lower input levels than the average of the normal-hearing group, representing a loudness for binaural broadband stimuli that is higher than expected from the hearing thresholds. ΔL_{40} can thus be interpreted as a metric for the individual binaural broadband loudness sensitivity. Figure 4 shows the cumulative distributions and boxplots of ΔL_{40} separated for the groups of participants. The distribution of normal-hearing participants is centred around the average defined as 0 dB, with extreme cases deviating approx. 15 dB. In all hearing-impaired participant groups, the distributions are shifted to the right, indicating an increased binaural broadband loudness sensitivity in the hearing-impaired participants. The distributions of both New and Experienced participants recruited in HAPFs are mostly equivalent but differ notably from that of the “Experiments” participants that were recruited from a research database. In the participants from the HAPFs, the distribution of ΔL_{40} is shifted to the right, indicating a higher proportion of individuals with high binaural broadband loudness sensitivity. The average observed values for ΔL_{40} are 8.1 dB for the Experimenters, and 13.2 dB for both the New and Experienced participants. An unpaired t -test did not show a significant difference between the predefined hearing-impaired participant groups in spite of these trends.

Figure 4: Distribution of excess binaural broadband loudness sensitivity, showing cumulative plot (bottom part) and boxplots (top part) separated by groups. Diamonds in top of the boxplots denote the mean of the distributions.

Among the hearing-impaired participants, the observed values of ΔL_{40} lie between -12.4 and 36.1 dB (2.5 and 97.5 percentiles), showing that the range of normal-hearing participants is met in the majority of individuals but exceeded by many. Using the 95th percentile of the normal-hearing data ($\Delta L_{40} = 17.2$ dB) as a value where the normal-hearing range is exceeded, it can be stated that a higher-than-normal binaural broadband loudness sensitivity is observed in 30 % of the Experimenters, and 38 and 39 % of New and Experienced hearing aid users from the field, respectively.

Figure 5 shows correlations between ΔL_{40} and other assessed audiological parameters. Statistically significant correlations are observed for the binaurally averaged PTA hearing threshold ($R^2 = .03, p = .033$), the IHS score ($R^2 = .03, p = .030$), the binaurally averaged PTA UCL ($R^2 = .06, p < .001$), and the speech signal UCL presented binaurally ($R^2 = .10, p < .001$) and the minimum of the speech signal UCL across ears with monaural presentation ($R^2 = .18, p < .001$). Although the correlations were statistically significant, the correlation coefficients are too low to indicate any predictive value on an individual basis. No correlations between age and ΔL_{40} were observed. IHS scores exceeding the threshold of 69 for

a likely hyperacusis (Greenberg and Carlos, 2018) were observed in only 5 participants, whose ΔL_{40} were well distributed across the typical hearing-impaired range (Figure 5, middle right panel). Further, a multi-linear regression model was fit to the data and reached an adjusted correlation coefficient of $R^2 = 0.21$. This showed that no linear combination of the assessed predictors resulted in a significantly better prediction than the minimum monaural speech UCL.

Figure 5: Correlations between the individual excess binaural broadband loudness sensitivity ΔL_{40} and other obtained audiological parameters (see x-axes). Green shaded area denotes the 90% range of normal-hearing participants. Text in the top right show square of linear correlation coefficients, stars indicate statistically significant correlation.

3.3. Prescribed Target Gain

Figure 6: Correlation of PTA gains and PTA hearing loss for all prescription rules and input levels with given value of R^2 . Boxplots show the distribution of PTA gains.

Figure 6 shows scatter plots between PTA hearing loss and average target gain at the PTA frequencies 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz for the three regarded prescription procedures and three input levels, together with boxplots of the average target gain distributions. Each ear is included separately. For NAL-NL2 and DSLm[i/o], high correlations around and above $R^2 = 0.9$ are observed at input levels 50 and 65 dB, i.e., these gains are prescribed mostly based on the threshold. At 80 dB input, this correlation reduces to $R^2 = 0.6$ and $R^2 = 0.68$ for DSLm[i/o] and NAL-NL2, respectively, showing a significant influence of other parameters. For DSLm[i/o], this is probably the provided UCL, while in NAL-NL2 the air-bone gap is used to complement the threshold to estimate the UCL. For trueLOUDNESS, the correlation of target gains and thresholds is generally lower, reaching $R^2 = 0.4$ at 50 dB input, and declining to $R^2 = 0.14$ at 80 dB. Although the correlation is still statistically significant, this shows that the hearing threshold has only minor influence for the trueLOUDNESS target gains at input levels of 65 and 80 dB.

It should be noted that the range of occurring gain values across all participants is similar in all prescription procedures for 50 and 65 dB, however, at specific PTA hearing losses the range is much higher for trueLOUDNESS than NAL-NL2 or DSLm[i/o]. At 80 dB, the distribution of prescribed gains is smaller in NAL-NL2 than in the other two gain rules, which show similar maximum gains but prescribe lower minimum gains. Other than NAL-NL2, both trueLOUDNESS and DSLm[i/o] prescribe negative gain targets for some individuals, most common at 80 dB input and for PTA hearing thresholds less than 50 dB HL.

Figure 7: Frequency-dependent compression ratios across several level ranges in the regarded gain rules according to Eq. (1) for level range given in the panel title and y-label. Boxplots show distributions of compression ratios from gain targets for the given frequency determined in all ears of New and Experienced participants (320 ears).

Figure 7 shows compression ratio distributions across ears at several frequencies and level ranges in the regarded gain rules. The top panel shows the full level range (80 vs. 50 dB input,

the middle panel the low-level range (65 vs. 50 dB input), and the lower panel the high-level range (80 vs. 65 dB input). Across all gain rules and frequencies, the compression ratio is smaller in the low and full level range than in the high-level range. The compression ratios for DSLm[i/o] are generally smaller than those observed in NAL-NL2 and trueLOUDNESS, and exceed a compression ratio of 2 only in few ears. In trueLOUDNESS and NAL-NL2, compression ratios tend to increase with frequency up to 4 kHz, following the average hearing thresholds that increases with frequency (c.f. Figure 1. The compression ratios with trueLOUDNESS are generally similar to those with NAL-NL2, but tend to be higher at 500 Hz (also below) and have a higher upper quartile range. Also, trueLOUDNESS shows cases with the lowest compressions ratios among all gain rules having compression ratios below 1. The highest median compression ratios between 4-5 with both gain rules are observed in the high-level regime at 4 kHz, with many cases exceeding a target compression ratio of 7.

Figure 8: Gain difference between trueLOUDNESS to NAL-NL2 (top row) and DSLm[i/o] (bottom row) prescriptive rules, separated by input level (see panel title) and frequency. Black boxplots show distributions across all ears, colors indicate grouping by the excess binuaral broadband loudness sensitivity (see legend). Percentages in legend denote the proportion of participants falling into the appropriate category.

Figure 8 shows the differences in target gains between trueLOUDNESS and the other two rules, separated by input level and frequency. The difference is shown by boxplots grouping all regarded participants (black), and grouped by the individual determined ΔL_{40} . Looking at the grouped results for all participants, the median differences between trueLOUDNESS and NAL-NL2 are below 5 dB, with a general tendency that trueLOUDNESS prescribes lower gains than NAL-NL2, except for 500 Hz (and below, not shown here) at low and intermediate input levels. Differences between both prescription procedures in individual ears amount to more than 20 dB in either direction, for all input levels and frequencies. The individual differences are explained largely by ΔL_{40} , where trueLOUDNESS gains in individuals with an average or slightly below average ΔL_{40} (green and light blue boxes in Figure 8) are closest to NAL-NL2.

Contrary, a high ΔL_{40} leads to trueLOUDNESS gains lower than those prescribed by NAL-NL2 and vice versa.

The differences between DSL and trueLOUDNESS depend on the level and frequency. At 50 dB input, trueLOUDNESS gains are 7-10 dB higher than DSL for the median participant. This difference declines towards higher input levels and is close to 0 dB at 80 dB input, except for 4 kHz where DSL prescribes a 5 dB lower gain on median. A similar range of individual deviations spanning close to 50 dB is observed, following a similar pattern depending on ΔL_{40} as for NAL-NL2. Based on correlation analysis of gains averaged across levels and frequencies, 76% and 88% of the difference between trueLOUDNESS and DSL and NAL-NL2 can be explained by ΔL_{40} , respectively.

Figure 9: Cumulative occurrence of gain differences between trueLOUDNESS and other fitting rules as denoted by panel title, unsigned average of differences across 500, 1000, 2000 and 4000 Hz, input levels of 50, 65 and 80 dB, and both ears of one participant.

Finally, Figure 9 shows the cumulative distributions of the average unsigned difference (see 2.3) between the trueLOUDNESS prescription procedures and the two reference rules. The predefined significant difference of 5 dB is exceeded for NAL-NL2 by approx. 45% of Experimenters participants, and 60% of both New and Experienced hearing aid customers from the HAPFs. The difference between trueLOUDNESS and NAL-NL2 tends to be largest in the New participants (showing as the shallowest curve), followed by Experienced listeners and the Experimenters group. Large differences exceeding 10 dB hardly occur for the Experimenters group, but in approx. 18 % of the Experienced and 30% of the New hearing aid customers. For the DSLm[i/o] rule, no obvious difference between participant groups is noted, and the 5 dB difference is exceeded in approx. 65% of all participants, and large differences exceeding 10 dB are observed in approx. 28% of all participants. Due to the observed differences between participants recruited from the database and HAPFs, only the New and Experienced participants were included for the following evaluations of gain differences.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Prevalence of increased binaural broadband loudness sensitivity in hearing-impaired listeners

A non-negligible proportion of hearing-impaired individuals showed a binaural broadband loudness sensitivity exceeding that of normal-hearing listeners. That is, using a categorical loudness scaling with a binaural broadband sound and level-dependent amplification aiming at narrowband loudness normalization based on the individual hearing thresholds, the sensitivity for loud sounds (measured at 40 CU) was increased by approx. 13 dB for the average hearing-impaired individual compared to the normal-hearing average. This difference decreases for softer sounds and increases for higher input levels. Large variations exist among hearing-impaired persons, with values ranging 10 dB below the normal-hearing average to 40 dB above it. Depending on the regarded group of participants, the loudness sensitivity can be regarded as

beyond the normal-hearing range in 30-40% of hearing-impaired individuals. We conclude that excess binaural broadband loudness sensitivity is a common and highly individual trait observed in a large proportion of hearing-impaired listeners.

The difference in excess binaural broadband loudness sensitivity between groups of participants in the present study emphasizes the potential impact of participant recruitment for characterizing hearing-impaired participants. Specifically, the excess binaural broadband loudness sensitivity was found to be lower in the “Experimenters” group recruited from a database that regularly participates in hearing studies, compared to the cohort recruited in the HAPFs. While this difference failed to reach statistical significance, we regard this result as relevant, given the visible differences of distributions. The distribution of excess binaural broadband loudness sensitivity in the Experimenters group is in excellent agreement with previous assessments of this effect (see supplemental file) that was conducted with participants from an independent but similar database of regular hearing-impaired participants of hearing studies (Oetting et al., 2017; Oetting, 2021). We speculate that the lower excess binaural broadband loudness sensitivity in this group of participants is caused by a sampling bias. It could be caused by the fact that hearing aid users with high excess loudness binaural broadband loudness sensitivity, who might perceive many situations as too loud, would be less inclined to regularly participate in hearing-aid related listening experiments.

Best efforts were made to recruit typical audiological patients seeking hearing aid treatment by inviting them directly during a hearing aid fitting session, with only minor effort or excessive measurements for them. However, sampling biases cannot be ruled out completely in this group of participants either. First, the data was obtained in some of the rather few HAPFs that had the measurement technique for the utilized loudness scaling measurement available. They are members of a first group of hearing aid professionals that regularly use the procedure of the scaling measurement and trueLOUDNESS prescription procedures, and it can be assumed they

were personally convinced of this approach. It can thus not be ruled out that the participants were influenced unintentionally by the operator of the experiment, although we consider the likelihood rather low given that the scaling measurement was highly automated. Although the participating hearing aid professionals were explicitly instructed to invite participants without any influence by their audiological performance, a sampling bias potentially vintaging recruiting participants with excess binaural broadband loudness sensitivity cannot be ruled out completely. One observation that speaks against a sampling bias in the hearing aid professionals' data is that New and Experienced participants showed virtually identical distributions of excess binaural broadband loudness sensitivity, where the characteristics of the New participants were to the largest extent unknown before they entered the experiments. It should be noted that some degree of loss of control about the experimental parameters is inevitably connected to data collection in the field as conducted in the present study. The present results highlight the importance of including listeners that would not be willing or be able to participate in laboratory studies into experiments characterizing hearing-impaired individuals.

We found no audiological diagnostic parameter that predicted the excess binaural broadband loudness sensitivity by itself or in a linear combination with any correlation close to clinical relevance (see Figure 5). Surprisingly, this also included also the IHS questionnaire on hyperacusis (Greenberg and Carlos, 2018), which was expected to correlate with perceived excess loudness especially in loud environments. We interpret this result as a sign of hyperacusis being a separate and rare condition where loud sounds generally lead to high discomfort, which should not be conflated with excess loudness perception when using hearing aids that is reported by many users. Also, it may seem surprising that the correlation between the excess binaural broadband loudness sensitivity measured by loudness scaling ΔL_{40} reached a significant but only weak correlation with UCLs measured with broadband speech signals (see Figure 5). However, two factors apparently contributed to a low correlation. On the one

hand, audibility across frequencies was not compensated in the UCL measurement with speech, leading to a reduced spectral loudness summation (Oetting et al., 2016). A different measurement signal such as pink noise could reduce this effect, however, it is very uncommon for measurements of UCLs and could be evaluated in further studies. On the other hand, the UCL is linked to a subjective response that is subject to significant variance (Punch et al., 2004), and differs methodically from the loudness scaling measurement. While a UCL measurement with an appropriate broadband test signal could be faster and easier to implement than loudness scaling at different frequencies, future research is required to determine the potential use to characterize individual binaural broadband loudness sensitivity.

4.2. Implications for hearing aid gain targets

The present data shows clearly that the individual gain targets obtained using trueLOUDNESS may deviate from established gain rules substantially. This deviation exceeded a predefined significance criterion in approximately half of all participants. While the average of trueLOUDNESS gain targets in the considered population is close to that of NAL-NL2, systematic differences between trueLOUDNESS and DSLm[i/o] were observed. Compared to trueLOUDNESS, DSLm[i/o] prescribes significantly lower gains at 50 and 65 dB input. Comparing trueLOUDNESS and NAL-NL2, the averages and distributions across participants are comparable both in terms of gain and compression ratios. Looking at the individual excess loudness sensitivity, the gain targets are most consistent in participants with a ΔL_{40} in the range of 15 dB below to 5 dB above the hearing-impaired average of 13 dB. Also from a correlation analysis it can be determined that the minimum difference between trueLOUDNESS and NAL-NL2 occurs for listeners with ΔL_{40} around 10 dB. This observation can be interpreted as NAL-NL2 having an excess loudness sensitivity slightly lower than the average of the present participants included. Given that NAL-NL2 was tested in a large group of hearing-impaired participants similar to the one assessed here and includes empirical adjustments on this basis

(Keidser et al., 2012) and has been in successful use for many years, this result provides further evidence for the existence of an excess loudness sensitivity in hearing-impaired listeners compared to the normal-hearing population. It should also be noted here that the range of individual fine-tuning adjustments to NAL-NL1 reported by Keidser et al. (2012) to achieve comfortable loudness well matches the range of differences to trueLOUDNESS in the present investigation.

Between trueLOUDNESS and both other prescription procedures there is a large inter-individual variation of the difference (c.f. Figure 8). This individual variation originates mostly from the variation across participants with similar thresholds in trueLOUDNESS (see Figure 6) and is determined largely by the individual binaural broadband loudness sensitivity (approx. 85% of variance explained). The highly individual difference between prescription procedures is a direct consequence of additional diagnostic information independent of the threshold that influences the trueLOUDNESS target, while NAL-NL2 and DSLm[i/o] mainly rely on the threshold. It can be argued based on these results that trueLOUDNESS leads to a higher degree of individualization in the target gains.

Finally, it should be stressed that the current data did not evaluate the validity or subjective fidelity of the assessed prescription procedures. However, the observed differences between gain rules can be expected to result in clearly distinguishable settings for the majority of participants, especially those with high excess loudness sensitivity. Future research is needed to evaluate whether the measurements going into the trueLOUDNESS prescription procedure indeed provide an improved loudness adjustment in everyday environments, and how speech intelligibility and other perceptually relevant parameters may be influenced by altered gain settings.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The present investigation showed that excess loudness sensitivity to binaural broadband sounds as compared to the normal-hearing population is a prevalent but highly individual trait in hearing-impaired listeners. In the present evaluation, approx. 40% of hearing-impaired individuals showed an excess loudness sensitivity beyond the normal-hearing range, with an average of 13 dB input level difference for a loud sound, and values up to 35 dB. The distributions of this excess loudness sensitivity varies between populations of hearing-impaired participants recruited in HAPFs and in a research database, showing the importance of participant recruitment that should be considered in further studies also on different aspects. A prescriptive procedure considering this individual trait led to large individual deviations from standard prescription procedures that are meaningful for more than half of all participants, while averages across participants are reasonably similar.

6. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

- The original data is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14190436>
- Pdf with supplementary plots is provided.

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